

Investigation by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy of Relaxation of Electrical Properties of Nanopowder System based on Zirconia after Baric Stress

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Abstract—By the method of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy the behavior of a dispersed system based on zirconia nanoparticles after exposure by high hydrostatic pressure was studied. It is established that high pressure initiates a long-term nonmonotonic process of structural relaxation, accompanied by a decrease in electrical conductivity. It is shown that the process consists of at least two stages differing in nature and rate of change in resistance.

Keywords—zirconia; nanopowder; electrical properties; high pressure

I. INTRODUCTION

Sealing is an integral part of technological process of consolidation of powders into bulk nanostructured products. Usually, a high hydrostatic pressure (HHP) is applied, providing a spatially uniform mechanical effect on a sample from outside [1].

During consolidating of nanoparticles the main task is to preserve grain size in nanoscale range with a minimum level of heterogeneity of a structure.

The behavior of a sample during sintering depends largely on a quality of a compact set [2]. The forces of interparticle interaction (electrostatic repulsion and van der Waals attraction), which determine the structure-energy state of a

dispersed system, have an electrical nature. That is, any changes in structural-energy state of a dispersed system will inevitably lead to a change in its electrical properties [3]. Investigation of the latter in relation to nanopowder oxide dispersed systems (NODS) at various stages of consolidation allows monitoring its thermodynamic and structural-energy state. It is an actual scientific task on the way to developing an industrial technology for production of bulk nanostructured oxide ceramics of complex shape.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is one of the methods that allow investigate electrical properties of NODS at various stages of consolidation [4, 5].

The aim of this work was to experimentally study electrical properties of NODS based on zirconia after influence by high hydrostatic pressure.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

As an object of investigation a compact sets from a nanopowder of composition $ZrO_2 + 3mol\% Y_2O_3$ were used. The technology for obtaining nanopowders is described in [6] and contains several technological operations. First, by coprecipitation method from nitrate raw material a hydrated zirconium hydroxide was prepared. After dehydration in a specialized microwave furnace ($T = 120^\circ C$, $t = 0.4$ h),

amorphous powder was subjected to crystallization annealing at a temperature of 400°C for 2 hours. Then, by uniaxial pressure ($P = 40\text{MPa}$) a compact sets in the form of tablets with a diameter of 20 and a height of the order of 1 mm (mass of a sample was 1g) were made. Immediately before compaction to unify the initial physical conditions, the powder was dried in a drying furnace at $T = 120^\circ\text{C}$, 1h, and then placed for 1h in a special climatic chamber with relative humidity level of $\eta = 70\%$ and a temperature of $T = 21^\circ\text{C}$. Almost immediately after compaction the tablets were sealed using a high hydrostatic pressure (500 MPa) [6]. 15 minutes after the HHP treatment, changes in electrical properties of the samples were measured at room temperature during 24 hours. A precision virtual meter-analyzer of the impedance parameters of type 2B-1 [7, 8] was used. Frequency dependences of imaginary and real components of the impedance of the samples under study were recorded. Amplitude of variable excitation signal was 50 mV, frequency range was 500 Hz - 1 MHz. Carbon electrodes were applied to wide sides of samples mechanically. Calculation of impedance parameters was carried out using the computer program EIS Spectrum Analyzer [9,10]. The methodology of the EIS studies in the author's version and its possibilities are detailed in [11].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hodographs of impedance and the equivalent circuit of the object under study (inset), which was used to calculate the conductivity, are shows on Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Hodographs of the samples measured after HHP treatment: (1) - after 15 minutes, (2) after 30 minutes, (3) after 45 minutes, (4) after 1 hour, (5) 1 hour 15 minutes. On the inset is an equivalent circuit used to calculate conductivity of the samples.

As can be seen from Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the hodographs have the form of semicircles with a center shifted below to the abscissa axis. As shown in [4, 12] and can be seen from [13, 14, 15], the shape of impedance hodograph of the NODS under study, as a rule, has the form similar to the type of spectra of objects with ionic conductivity type, in particular, elements of lithium chemical current sources. This is due to the presence of

ionic atmosphere of adsorption origin in nanopowder objects. Therefore, beyond the resolution of the spectrometer in a low-frequency range there is at least one more ray with an angle of inclination to the axis of abscissa of 45° , that characterizing conductivity in a space between particles [16]. Due to high resistance of the object under study, in our case it outside the operating range of the spectrometer. The shape of the curves on Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 means the capacitive nature of conductivity of the objects. Consequently, it characterizes the electrical process in a bulk of dielectric material. Thus, hodographs on Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 reflects electrical properties of nanoparticles material.

In this case, the resistive-capacitive properties of the system under investigation are satisfactorily approximated by an equivalent circuit using a constant phase element (Fig. 1, insert) [17]. Each element of an equivalent circuit characterizes one or another physical or electrochemical process that takes place in a real cell under study. There are certain structural elements that responsible for transfer of charge in a material. Such elements in the NODS under investigation with a high degree of probability are polar complexes of structural defects: impurity-vacancy dipoles (IVD) [18, 19]. They appear as follows.

In a solid substitution solution based on zirconia, the impurity atoms Y^{3+} has one electron less than the Zr^{4+} atoms. It is acceptors. Oxygen vacancies formed for compensation of excess volume and charge of the inovalent impurity are electron donors. Acceptor and donor character of the tetragonal modification of a solid solution based on zirconia ($\beta\text{-ZrO}_2$) for Y^{3+} and oxygen vacancies, respectively, is confirmed by the results of [20]. Roughly speaking, as a result of thermal fluctuations, the holes give an electron to the conduction band (ionization of the hole), which by a Coulomb interaction finds an impurity atom and hits its orbital [21]. The above-mentioned IVD of type Me-V_O is formed, and the corresponding ionic bond according to [22] is the stabilizing element of the lattice (β -phase). In this case, the impurity atom $\text{Me} \equiv \text{Y}^{3+}$ acquires a negative charge $\text{Y}^{3+(-)}$, and the vacancy $\text{V}_O \equiv \text{V}$ is positive $\text{V}^{(+)}$. That is, donors and acceptors co-exist in the form of bound charges, which are IVD of a type $\text{V}^{(+)} - \text{Y}^{3+(-)}$. Concentrations of donors and acceptors balance each other and there is no shortage (or excess) of electrons in comparison with their quantity necessary for the ionic bonding. The binding energy varies inversely with the distance, therefore, there are always pairs capable of complex formation even under very weak energy effects, in particular, at room temperatures [23].

By cyclic polarization of the IVD, probable, energy transfer of alternating electric field in the dielectric volume of ZrO_2 nanoparticle material, is carried out.

A slight asymmetry of a shape of presented experimental curves indicates a deviation from ideality. From Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 it is clear that the radius of the circles increases with increasing of aftereffect time.

Conductivity was calculated by the formula:

$$\sigma = \frac{l}{SR},$$

where l is a thickness of a sample, S is a cross-sectional area of a sample, R is a sample resistance obtained from equivalent electrical circuit.

Fig. 2. Hodographs of samples after HHP treatment: (1) - after 15 minutes, (2) - 6 hours and (3) - 24 hours.

Values of conductivity versus time after HHP treatment are shown on Fig. 3. As can be seen from Fig. 3, in the process of curing value of the resistance of the samples is increases.

In the framework of the model used to transmit the energy of an alternating electric signal through the polarization of defect complexes localized in the bulk of a dielectric, decrease in conductivity can be a consequence of the enlargement of the latter due to the association of IVD. The point is that the IVD is associated in complexes for reduction of free energy.

Fig. 3. Dependence of conductivity of samples on time after the baric effect.

Impurity-vacancy defect complexes (IVDC) are constantly in a state of unstable thermodynamic equilibrium. Even a slight change in external conditions causes their rearrangement in the direction of lowering the value of free energy [24]. For example, an increase in temperature will initiate dissociation of IVDC, and a decrease - its association. In the first case, due to the increase in polarizability of polar groups, conductivity and frequency properties of the material increase, whereas in the second case, on the contrary, they decrease.

The dimensions of the IVDC, which prevail at the time of measurement in the material, under the condition of invariable

polarizability of the IVDC components, can be indirectly judged by the magnitude of the amplitude (maximum) values of the material's own times. Let us consider how the investigated NODS behave in the process of relaxation.

The maximum values of the imaginary part of impedance ImZ , which characterizes the amplitude value of the sample capacitive resistance, for the hodographs obtained as an example after 15 minutes, 6 and 24 hours after HHP treatment, are observed at frequencies ω_m equal to 5649, 2515 and 2962 Hz, respectively. The corresponding own times of the structural elements $\tau = 1/\omega_m$, by means of which the capacitive conductivity of a sample is assumed (presumably, IVDC) according to the used model are presented in Table 1 and on Fig. 4.

It can be seen that in the process of relaxation, own times τ , and consequently, sizes of the structural elements that carry out mainly capacitive conductivity in the volume of dielectric nanoparticles increased by 2.2 times during the time of aging (24 h). In addition, (Table 1, Figure 4), dynamics of relaxation processes during first 90 min after HHP influence was accompanied by a periodic change in own times. The value of τ periodically varied from $1.77 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $2.08 \div 2.87 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s.

Fig. 4. Own times $\tau = 1 / \omega_m$ of structural elements of a sample as a function of time after the HHP treatment, where ω_m is frequency at which the amplitude value of imaginary part of impedance is reached.

TABLE I. VALUES OF IMAGINARY PART OF CONDUCTIVITY AND CALCULATED OWN TIMES OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS AS A FUNCTION OF TIME AFTER HHP TREATMENT.

Time after HHP treatment, h	ImZ_{max} , Ohm	ω_m , Hz	Own times of structural elements, s
0.25	$5.67 \cdot 10^{+05}$	5649.717	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-04}$
0.5	$5.61 \cdot 10^{+05}$	4807.692	$2.08 \cdot 10^{-04}$
0.75	$6.42 \cdot 10^{+05}$	5649.717	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-04}$
1	$7.14 \cdot 10^{+05}$	5649.717	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-04}$
1.25	$7.20 \cdot 10^{+05}$	3484.321	$2.87 \cdot 10^{-04}$
1.5	$7.34 \cdot 10^{+05}$	4098.361	$2.44 \cdot 10^{-04}$
6	$9.28 \cdot 10^{+05}$	2515.723	$3.98 \cdot 10^{-04}$
24	$1.64 \cdot 10^{+05}$	2515.723	$3.97 \cdot 10^{-04}$

This behavior of the system can be caused by competitive dynamics of simultaneously occurring processes at a level of subsystem of structural defects. One of processes is accompanied by a decrease in average number of structural elements in defective complexes and another - by their increase.

Further aging ($t > 90$ min) is accompanied by a relatively rapid decrease in conductivity of the samples. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the rate of structure-forming relaxation processes during the first 6 hours was more than 3 times higher than during aging for the next 18 hours (0.1 s^{-1} and 0.03 s^{-1} , respectively). This fact indicates a change in the nature of relaxation process, probably as a result of the suppression of the process aimed at dissociation of structural elements in polar defect complexes. Thus, the analysis of own times of structural elements through which conductivity in the bulk of nanoparticles is carried out is indicate a nonmonotonic character of the structure-forming processes initiated by HHP.

In particular, within the framework of assumption of correspondence between spectrum of frequencies of EIS measurements and the set of polar structural elements of the system with the corresponding time parameters τ , it can be asserted that relaxation process in investigated NODS after the HHP effect is accompanied by a nonmonotonic increase in size of polar structural complexes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

1. It has been established that HHP initiates in the dispersed system a long-term nonmonotonic process of structural relaxation, accompanied by a decrease in electrical conductivity. It is shown that the process consists of at least two stages differing in the nature and rate of change in resistance. It is established that at the first stage (the first 6 hours) average dynamics of the resistance change is in 3.3 times higher than at the second stage ($6 < t < 24$ h) (0.1 s^{-1} and 0.03 s^{-1} , respectively).

2. It is shown that the EIS method applied to NODS has an extremely high sensitivity and allows fixing changes in the impedance and the frequency spectrum of polar structural elements of nanoparticles material, which allows establishing the relationship between spatial and temporal characteristics.

3. Within the framework of the assumption that temporal and spatial characteristics of the polar structural elements of nanoparticles material (the reaction time of the polar substance versus its size) it was shown that the two-stage process of structure formation at the first stage of relaxation ($t < 6$ h) is nonmonotonic: own time of these elements periodically varies from $1.77 \cdot 10^{-04}$ to $2.08 \div 2.87 \cdot 10^{-04}$ s. It is assumed that periodic change in resistance at the first stage of structure formation is due to the competitive dynamics of two independent processes accompanied by a change in size of polar defect complexes of $Y^{3+(-)} - V^{-(+)}$ type.

4. It was shown that the EIS technique allows fixing the HHP-initiated change in charge state of a sample - a

nanopowder compact set, and the investigated nanopowder system is sensitive to a change in the external pressure.

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